

Adsorption efficiency of magnetite nanoparticles for chromium(VI) removal from water

Madhu Agarwal*, Pritam Dey, Sushant Upadhyaya and Rajeev Dohare

Department of Chemical Engineering, Malaviya National Institute of Technology, Jaipur-302 017, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : madhunaresh@gmail.com, magarwal.chem@mnit.ac.in

Manuscript received online 17 January 2015, revised 09 May 2015, accepted 09 June 2015

Abstract : Iron oxide nanoparticles were synthesized and used to remove hexavalent chromium from water solution and tannery effluent. SEM images showed that the nanoparticles were spheroid-shaped and in clustered forms. The average sizes of 15.38 nm for these nanoparticles were determined using diffraction analysis. FT-IR spectrum revealed those functional groups which were responsible for adsorption of chromium species. Batch adsorption studies suggested that pH of 2.0 and a temperature of 30 °C was optimum to achieved highest chromium removal. The adsorption process followed pseudo-second order kinetic model and there was no intra-particle diffusion in these nanoparticles. The process of Cr^{VI} sorption on iron oxide nanoparticles followed Langmuir isotherm and the maximum Cr^{VI} adsorptive capacity was found out as 16.3934 mg/g. Thermodynamic analysis revealed that the adsorption process was spontaneous and endothermic, while randomness increased at the solid-liquid interface during Cr^{VI} adsorption. These nanoparticles achieved 72.45% Cr^{VI} removal from tannery effluent.

Keywords : Hexavalent chromium, iron oxide nanoparticles, magnetite nanoparticles, adsorption, tannery effluent.

Introduction

As we all know more than ninety percent of industries (mostly in developing countries) do not treat their liquid waste before discharging it into the open sinks. These waters are laden with toxic substances of different kinds, causing different types of ill-effects to our health. Heavy metals comprise such a group of substances which have serious implications on our health. Heavy metal toxicity has been a major worry among environmentalists all around the globe. These metal ions from metal mining pose problems to the water environment by discharging mine water from underground and open pit mines¹. One of these heavy metals is chromium, which is highly toxic in its hexavalent oxidation state and is considered a carcinogen. Its main sources are tanning, electroplating, smelting and mining industries, from where it is dumped into open water bodies without even pondering upon its deadly effects on aquatic and human lives. Chromium is released into the environment from electroplating, anodizing, metal finishing, tannery, dying and fertilizer industries^{2,3}. It is estimated that more than 90% of the global production of leather receives chromium as a tanning agent during dif-

ferent stages of processing⁴. Therefore, the tanning industry is responsible for the generation of large quantities of chromium wastes such as effluents, sludge, and solid residue. As per Indian standard specifications for drinking water, the maximum permissible limit for chromium to be present in drinking water is 0.05 mg/L. Total chromium in drinking water and inland surface waters, in the USA is stipulated by the Environmental Protection Agency⁵ to be 0.1 mg/L. As per WHO standards, the maximum permissible limit for chromium in drinking water is 0.05 mg/L⁶.

In natural systems, chromium exists almost exclusively in the oxidation state of trivalent Cr^{III} and hexavalent Cr^{VI}. Normally, industrial waste also contains both hexavalent and trivalent forms of chromium. The geochemistry of chromium is complex due to its redox activity by which Cr readily converts between Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI}. Chromium(VI) has been classified as a "Class A" human carcinogen due to the strong oxidative properties causing genotoxic effects on DNA^{7,8}. The strong oxidative properties of Cr^{VI} also lead to acute oral and dermatological toxicity^{9,10}. In contrast, Cr^{III} is regarded as an essential

dietary micronutrient for sugar and lipid metabolism^{11,12}.

Conventional process to remove the Cr^{VI} by precipitation or ion exchange are not completely satisfactory and have several disadvantages. Among all these techniques, adsorption is the most promising technique and feasible alternatives¹³⁻¹⁵. Adsorption offers significant advantages like low cost, availability, profitability, ease of operation and efficiency, in comparison with conventional methods (such as membrane filtration or ion exchange) especially from economic and environmental points of view¹⁶⁻¹⁹. A variety of natural and synthetic materials has been used as Cr^{VI} sorbents, including activated carbons, biological materials, zeolites, chitosan, and industrial wastes²⁰.

Nanomaterial is the all-encompassing class of materials with at least one nanoscale feature, such as particle size and pore diameter²⁰. A wide variety of metal nanoparticles have been widely synthesized and used in both industries and research purposes. Iron oxide nanoparticles, mainly those comprising of hematite (α -Fe₂O₃), magnetite (Fe₃O₄) and maghemite (γ -Fe₂O₃), are in much use because of their magnetic, super-magnetic and antimagnetic properties²¹. Magnetic nanoparticles show remarkable phenomena such as super paramagnetism, high saturation field, high field irreversibility, extra anisotropy contributions or shifted loops after field cooling which arise from their very finite size and surface properties that dominate the magnetic behaviour of individual nanoparticles²². Various synthesis techniques were used for the synthesis of iron oxide nanoparticles, such as hy-

drothermal method, sono-chemical synthesis, sol-gel reactions, and chemical precipitation²³. The size, shape, and composition of the magnetic nanoparticles very much depends on the type of salts used (e.g. chlorides, sulfates, nitrates), the Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ ratio, the reaction temperature, the pH value and ionic strength of the media^{24,25}.

In this study, magnetite nanoparticles were synthesized using co-precipitation method and were used in batch study to determine kinetic and thermodynamic parameters for hexavalent chromium removal. Later on, a tannery effluent was also treated with these nanoparticles to show their applicability in industrial wastewater treatment.

Results and discussion

The SEM micrographs of nanoparticles were shown in Fig. 1. A high degree of agglomeration can be seen in figure. The smaller iron oxide nanoparticles (size range : 10–30 nm) got clumped together to form large chunks of iron oxide particles in micro meter range.

The XRD pattern showed in Fig. 2 revealed high intensity line with distinguishable peaks at 30.34, 35.65°, 43.32°, 54.48°, 57.64° and 63.02 which are in accordance to the peaks obtained by other researchers²⁶⁻²⁸ for magnetite nanoparticles. The grain size of nanoparticles from peaks 35.65° was determined using Debye-Scherrer formula as mentioned above and it was found to be 15.38 nm.

The FT-IR spectrum plots for bare iron oxide nanoparticles (a) and iron oxide nanoparticles upon adsorbing chromium(VI) ions from aqueous solution was

Fig. 1. SEM images of synthesized magnetite nanoparticles before (a) and after adsorption (b).

Fig. 2. XRD pattern of synthesized iron oxide nanoparticles.

shown in Fig. 3. The FT-IR spectrum shows a predominant peak at 668.93 cm^{-1} which corresponds to Fe-O bonding, also, peaks at 3406.79 cm^{-1} , 1385.12 cm^{-1} and 3019.48 cm^{-1} corresponds to O-H stretching vibrations, $-\text{NH}_2$ groups and N-H bending vibrations, respectively. The N-H, $-\text{NH}_2$ and O-H bonds represent the residual ammonium hydroxide solution present on the nanoparticle surface. It is evident from the report of Cornell and Schwertmann²⁹ that the most dominant functional groups on magnetite surface, which corresponds to Fe^{2+} and its hydrolysis products, are FeOH^+ , $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^0$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3^-$. Therefore, groups could readily attract Cr^{6+} and its negative species (HCrO_4^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$). Upon investigating the Cr^{VI} adsorbed nanoparticles, it was found that the O-H stretching have shifted to 3383 cm^{-1} and 3019.59 cm^{-1} . Also, there is a slight shift of Fe-O peak from 668.93 cm^{-1} to 668.59 cm^{-1} which suggest surface phenomena of adsorption has taken place.

Effect of operating parameters :

The effect of solution pH on chromium removal was investigated and reported in Fig. 4. The figure clearly shows that chromium removal was favored at very low pH range 1.5 to 2.0. At pH greater than 2.5, the removal decreased drastically from 96.43% (at pH 2.0) to 69.78% (at pH 4.0). The removal efficiency went on decreasing as pH increased and at pH 10.0 it was lowest (46.38%). Similar trend was observed when the initial chromium concentration was changed to 100 mg/L.

Chromium oxidation state in a solution is a strong function of pH. Under inert environment, between pH 0 to 2.5, Cr^{III} is the dominant species; between pH 3.0 to 5.5, CrO_4^{2-} predominates, between pH values 5.5 to 7.5 CrO_4^{2-} and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ exist simultaneously and above pH 7.5 till 14, CrO_4^{2-} is the dominant species³⁰. It has also been reported that no sorbent is efficient enough to remove Cr^{VI} from solutions at higher pH values³¹.

Fig. 3. FT-IR spectrum for iron oxide nanoparticles : (a) after synthesis and (b) upon adsorption of Cr^{VI} .

Fig. 4. Effect of initial pH of solution on Cr^{VI} removal efficiency (50 and 100 mg/L Cr^{VI} concentration, 4 g/L dosage, 4 h contact time, 25 °C temp., 250 rpm).

A detailed experimental investigation was done to find out the equilibrium time for iron oxide nanoparticles to adsorb maximum Cr^{VI} from aqueous solution, results obtained were represented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Effect of contact time on Cr^{VI} removal efficiency (Parameters : 50 and 100 mg/L initial Cr^{VI} concentration, 4 g/L dosage, pH 2.0, 25 °C temp., 250 rpm).

It can be clearly observed that the changes in removal efficiency of iron oxide nanoparticles with respect to contact time followed a logarithmic pattern till 60 min. After 60 min, the removal efficiency decreases and started saturating as evident by an almost linear curve. This may be because of saturation of available active sites on the adsorbents surface. The active sites present on magnetite nanoparticles are different than the microporous sites present in any porous adsorbents³², here the externally adsorbed chromium species may cause hindrance to remaining chromium species to be adsorbed. At 4 h of contact time the Cr^{VI} removal efficiency reached 96.43% which remained almost constant till 7 h. Hence, the equi-

librium time of 4 h was selected for rest of experiments. At this time period, 12.05375 mg/g of Cr^{VI} had been adsorbed by iron oxide nanoparticles.

A comprehensive study on the effect of initial Cr^{VI} concentration on its removal using iron oxide nanoparticles was conducted at two different nanoparticle dosages (2 g/L and 4 g/L), results were shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Effect of initial Cr^{VI} concentration on removal efficiency (Parameters : 2 and 4 g/L dosage, pH 2.0, 4 h contact time, 25 °C temp., 250 rpm).

It is well evident from above figure that the percentage chromium removal was inversely proportional to the initial chromium concentration in the solution. Almost 100% removal was obtained at lower initial concentration however, with increase in chromium concentration removal started decreasing. Similar trend was reported by many researchers³³. The difference in removal percentage was increased and very high for two adsorption dosage after 75 mg/L of initial chromium concentration. The reason for such may be due to saturation of adsorbent sites at higher concentrations.

The effect of adsorbent amount on chromium removal was studied and results obtained were shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Effect of nanoparticles dosage on Cr^{VI} removal efficiency. (Parameters : 50 and 100 mg/L Cr^{VI} concentration, pH 2.0, 4 h contact time, 25 °C temp., 250 rpm).

As shown in Fig. 7, the percent removal of Cr^{VI} increased as amount of nanoparticles in the system increased. The removal efficiency increased almost linearly for both initial Cr^{VI} concentrations up to 4 g/L of adsorbent dose, after that it became almost constant. This behavior could be explained by the fact that when dosage was low, the amount of adsorbate per gram adsorbent was high, i.e. limited active site for adsorption caused low adsorption. As the amount of nanoparticles in the solution was increased the removal efficiency also increased. But after a point, even with increased dose, removal remained constant. This may be because saturation of active sites or nanoparticles had reached their equilibrium uptake/adsorption capacity (which is fixed for an adsorbent at particular values of pH and temperature). Thus, the equilibrium dosage of iron oxide nanoparticles for Cr^{VI} removal was selected as 4 g/L for 50 mg/L initial Cr^{VI} concentration and 6 g/L for 100 mg/L initial concentration.

A comprehensive study on the effects of operating temperature on Cr^{VI} removal has been carried out in this work. For this a temperature variation of 5 °C was used while keeping all other operating parameters the same as what has been optimized above as shown in Fig. 8 below.

Fig. 8. Effect of incubating temperature on Cr^{VI} removal efficiency (Parameters : 50 mg/L initial Cr^{VI} concentration, 4 g/L dosage, pH 2.0, 4 h contact time, 250 rpm).

As it is evident from the graph, removal of Cr^{VI} started increasing as temperature increased till 30 °C. After which the percent removal started decreasing. The increase in removal of Cr^{VI} as temperature increased from 20 °C to 30 °C was because of increase in thermal energy of molecules for adsorption. The decrease in adsorption at temperature higher than 30 °C may be due to desorption of

chromium species from nanoparticle surface³⁴. Also, between temperature of 35 °C and 40 °C, removal was almost identical pointing out a wide temperature to work with iron oxide nanoparticles.

To understand the behavior of synthesized iron oxide nanoparticles in an environment consisting of various heavy metal ions (which is a practical situation as most industrial wastes contain many heavy metal ions) and to evaluate its Cr^{VI} removing capabilities, batch experiments were conducted with two other heavy metals. The initial Cr^{VI} concentration was kept fixed along with the other parameters (which were optimized in the previous experiments) with the concentrations of Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} were varied.

As shown in Fig. 9 the presence of Pb^{II} alone assisted in Cr^{VI} removal whereas, Cd^{II} when present reduced the percent removal. Also, the concentrations of these heavy metals influenced Cr^{VI} removal from the mixed solution. It can be inferred that Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} played antagonistic roles in Cr^{VI} removal from a mixed solution containing these two metals. Even when Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} were present in equal amount, Cd^{II} overpowered Pb^{II} and brought down the removal efficiency. This proves that Cd^{II} and Cr^{VI} competes for a few similar adsorption site on bare iron oxide nanoparticles at the optimized conditions whereas Pb^{II} is adsorbed on quite different sites.

Fig. 9. Effects of Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} upon Cr^{VI} removal efficiency (Parameters : 50 mg/L Cr^{VI} concentration, 4 g/L dosage, pH 2.0, 4 h contact time, 30 °C temp., 250 rpm).

After successful separation of nanoparticles from the aqueous solution after a round of batch adsorption cycle, the nanoparticles were reused for batch run under the optimized conditions. The percentage chromium removal decreased as the cycles increased, but even after third

cycle of reuse, 60.85% chromium was removed from the solution. This showed that the nanoparticles were study enough to be used till five cycles before decreasing their yields to less than half of what was in the initial run.

Adsorption kinetics :

Four adsorption kinetics models, pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order and intra-particle diffusion, were investigated using eqs. (1)-(4) to get the best fit which could describe the adsorption mechanism.

Lagregen's pseudo-first order kinetics³⁵ :

$$\log(Q_e - Q_t) = \log Q_e - \frac{k_1}{2.303} t \quad (1)$$

Ho's pseudo-second order kinetics³⁶ :

$$\frac{t}{Q_t} = \frac{1}{K_2 Q_e^2} + \frac{t}{Q_e} \quad (2)$$

Bangham's kinetics³⁷ :

$$\frac{C_0}{C_0 - Q} = \log\left(\frac{k_0 m}{2.303V}\right) + \alpha \log t \quad (3)$$

Weber's intra-particle diffusion kinetics³⁸ :

$$Q_t = k_{id} t^{1/2} + C \quad (4)$$

where, Q_e (mg/g) and Q_t (mg/g) are adsorption capacities at equilibrium and time (t) (min), k_1 (min^{-1}) is first order rate constant, k_2 (g/mg min) is rate constant for second order, C_0 is initial concentration (mg), V is volume of solution (mL), M is weight of the adsorbent (g/L) and α , k_0 are constants, C is constant and k_{id} is intra-particle diffusion rate constant ($\text{mg/g h}^{1/2}$). The experimental data fitting to the above models were presented in Fig. 10 and the kinetic constants thus obtained were listed in Table 1.

It is evident from Fig. 10 that Cr^{VI} adsorption onto iron oxide nanoparticles follows pseudo-second order kinetics because of very high value for coefficient of corre-

Fig. 10. Plots for different adsorption kinetic models : (a) pseudo-first order and (b) pseudo-second order kinetics, (c) Bangham kinetics and (d) intra-particle diffusion model (Parameters : 4 g/L dosage, pH 2.0, 25 °C temp. and 250 rpm).

Table 1. Rate constants for different adsorption kinetic models

Kinetic model	Constants and correlation coefficient	Value	
		$C_0 = 50$ (mg/L)	$C_0 = 100$ (mg/L)
Pseudo-first order kinetics	k_1 (min^{-1})	1.54×10^{-3}	7.6×10^{-3}
	Q_e (mg/g)	5.2529	8.0445
	R^2	0.9263	0.9074
	R.M.S. error	0.14959	0.12683
Pseudo-second order kinetics	k_2 (g/mg min)	6.48×10^{-3}	1.47×10^{-3}
	Q_e (mg/g)	12.5	11.8624
	R^2	0.9845	0.9997
	R.M.S. error	0.20713	1.67046
Bangham's model	k_0	6232.093	5271.497
	α	0.1161	0.0591
	R^2	0.8976	0.9710
	R.M.S. error	0.17403	0.09268
Intra-particle diffusional model	k_{id}	0.2908	0.43
	C	7.0798	2.3456
	R^2	0.7172	0.9683
	R.M.S. error	0.16999	0.12198

lation (0.9997 for $C_0 = 100$ mg/L and 0.9845 for $C_0 = 50$ mg/L).

This result is in accordance to results of many researches on Cr^{VI} sorption onto nanomaterials^{39,40}. Also, from the Table 1, pseudo-second order kinetics the value of Q_e (18.86 mg/g) was in agreement to the experimental value. From intra-particle diffusion kinetic plot it can be inferred that there is no pore diffusional effects and the whole adsorption process took place on the nanoparticle surface only. This statement is validated by the fact that the fitted lines for intra-particle diffusion don't pass through the origin (due to non-zero values for C) and also the adsorption data didn't fit well with this model. But, it also suggested that there may be other mass transfer phenomena working alongside surface adsorption during the process of chromium adsorption on magnetite nanoparticles.

Adsorption isotherms :

Adsorption equilibria provide fundamental physico-chemical data for evaluating the applicability of the adsorption process as a unit operation⁴¹. Equilibrium adsorption isotherms are very necessary in studying the phenomenon of adsorption as they give an idea about the mechanism of adsorption and the maximum adsorption capacity of a particular adsorbate. The four major adsorp-

tion isotherms (eqs. (5)-(8)), were investigated in the present work and reported in Fig. 11(a-d) :

Langmuir isotherm⁴² :

$$\frac{C_e}{Q_e} = \frac{1}{K_L Q_{\max}} + \frac{C_e}{Q_{\max}} \quad (5)$$

Freundlich isotherm⁴³ :

$$\ln Q_e = \ln K_F + \frac{1}{n} \ln C_e \quad (6)$$

Henry isotherm³⁷ :

$$Q_e = K_H C_e \quad (7)$$

Temkin isotherm⁴⁴ :

$$Q_e = \frac{RT}{b} \ln C_e + \frac{RT}{b} \ln A \quad (8)$$

where, C_e (mg/L) is equilibrium solute concentration, Q_e (mg/g) adsorption capacity at equilibrium, K_L is Langmuir constant, Q_{\max} (mg/g) is maximum adsorption capacity, K_F (mg/g) and n are Freundlich constants, K_H (L/g) is Henry constant, b and A are Temkin constants, R is universal gas constant and T is operating temperature.

Moreover, other essential characteristics of Langmuir isotherm called separation factor (R_L)^{45,46} was also determined using eq. (9) and shown in Fig. 11(e) :

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + K_L C_0} \quad (9)$$

where, C_0 is the initial Cr^{VI} concentration (mg/L) and K_L is the Langmuir constant (L/mg). The value of R_L , between zero and one indicate favorable adsorption.

The best fitting was achieved in Langmuir isotherm, while Temkin was the least fitted one. The value of correlation coefficient (R^2) along with isotherm model constants were presented in Table 2. The high value of R^2 for Langmuir model indicate that the adsorption of Cr^{VI} on nanoparticles surface was homogeneous and monolayer in nature. The maximum possible Cr^{VI} adsorption by bare magnetite (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles determined from the Langmuir isotherm fitting was 16.39 mg/g.

The calculated values of separation factors versus initial solute concentration shown in Fig. 11(e) indicate that the adsorption was favorable ($R_L < 0.04$) under experimental conditions.

Fig. 11. Isotherms for adsorption of Cr^{VI} on iron oxide nanoparticles. (a) Langmuir, (b) Freundlich, (c) Henry and (d) Temkin isotherm. (Parameters : pH 2.0, 25 °C temp. 4 h contact time and 250 rpm). (e) Separation factor (R_L) for Cr^{VI} adsorption on iron oxide nanoparticles at two different dosages.

Adsorption thermodynamics :

Thermodynamic parameters like standard enthalpy change (ΔH°), standard entropy change (ΔS°), and standard Gibbs energy (ΔG°) of adsorption were calculated for the adsorption process using eqs. (10)-(12).

$$K_d = \frac{Q_e}{C_e} \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_d \quad (11)$$

$$\ln K_d = \frac{\Delta S^\circ}{R} - \frac{\Delta H^\circ}{RT} \quad (12)$$

where, R is the Universal gas constant ($R = 8.314 \text{ J/mol K}$) and T is the temperature of the process (K). K_d is called the distribution constant or thermodynamic equilibrium constant. Based on the distribution constant and uti-

Table 2. Parameters of different isotherms investigated

Isotherms	Parameters	Values	
		4 g/L NP	2 g/L NP
Langmuir	Q_{\max} (mg/g)	16.3934	12.1065
	K_L (L/mg)	3.3899	1.0274
	R^2	0.9989	0.9991
	R.M.S. error	0.02683	0.02582
Freundlich	K_F (mg/g)	11.8394	8.7364
	n	9.3371	12.356
	R^2	0.7182	0.7535
	R.M.S. error	0.08554	0.05852
Henry	K_H (L/g)	0.9579	0.3131
	R^2	0.7864	0.7806
	R.M.S. error	1.71468	1.05041
Temkin	A	8.74×10^8	4.36×10^4
	b_T	6.52×10^3	3.05×10^3
	R^2	0.7675	0.7101
	R.M.S. error	1.40946	0.60904

lizing the above equations (ΔH^0), (ΔS^0) and (ΔG^0) were calculated from Fig. 12.

The values of ΔG^0 decreased from -3.6 kJ/mol to -15.6 kJ/mol as temperature increased from 20 to 40 °C. After that, ΔG^0 started increasing with temperature. The negative value ΔG^0 and the positive value of ΔH^0 (42.33 kJ/mol) suggested that the adsorption of Cr^{VI} on iron oxide nanoparticles was spontaneous and endothermic in nature. The positive value of ΔS^0 (157.3 J/mol) suggested that randomness increased at solid-liquid interface during Cr^{VI} ion adsorption onto iron oxide nanoparticles.

The characteristics of tannery effluent obtained from leather industry in Kanpur were reported in Table 3.

Fig. 12. Adsorption thermodynamics of Cr^{VI} on iron oxide.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of high purity and purchased from local market. Magnetite nanoparticles were synthesized using co-precipitation method⁴⁷, in a typical experiment 50 ml ferric chloride hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and 50 ml of ferrous chloride tetrahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were mixed at a molar ratio of 2 : 1. This stoichiometric mixture was stirred at on a magnetic stirrer with a hot plate at temperature 70 °C, with addition of 25% ammonia solution dropwise till the pH reached around 9. At this condition, the solution turned rust-like greenish in colour due to the formation of ferrous hydroxide. Stirring was continued for another 45 min. In the meanwhile, the solution turned brownish black in colour. After which, the nanoparticles were allowed to settle down and the supernatant water was removed without disturbing the settled particles by magnetic decantation using a strong magnetic bar. Particles were dried and characterized by XRD (Bruker D-8, Germany), SEM (Zeiss EVO 18 special edition, Oxford Instruments Ltd., England), FTIR (Perkin-Elmer) etc. The crystal size was determined by using Debye-Scherrer's equation⁴⁸ :

$$d = \frac{K\lambda}{B \cos \theta_B} \quad (13)$$

where, d is the grain size (Å), K is called the shape factor (~ 0.89 to 0.94), λ is the operating wavelength (~ 1.54 nm), B is the full width of peak at half maximum and θ_B is the Bragg's angle.

The batch studies for chromium removal were conducted under controlled environment in a standard orbital shaker incubator. A series of experiments were carried out. In a typical experiment 100 ml of Cr^{VI} solution (concentration 25 mg/L to 100 mg/L) was taken in 250 ml conical flask and synthesized nanoparticles (dosage 1 g/L to 6 g/L) were added, the mixture was stirred at constant pH (varying from 1.0 to 10.0), temperature (25 to 50 °C) and time (15 min to 7 h), after that mixture was filter and filtrate was analysed for remaining chromium in the solution by means of standard diphenylcarbazide (DPC) method spectrophotometrically (Shimadzu UV 1800) at 540 nm wavelength.

Table 3. Characteristics of tannery effluent from a tannery industry in Kanpur

Color	pH	Conductivity (mS/cm)	TSS (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)	COD (mg/L)	Cr (mg/L)
Brown to lighttan color	6.74	6.95	12500	540	1360	68.56

The above effluent was contacted with iron oxide nanoparticles at the optimized conditions in batch reactor and 72.45% removal was achieved.

Percentage of Cr^{VI} removed from the original solution was determined by the formula :

$$\% \text{ Removal} = (1 - C_f/C_i) \times 100 \quad (14)$$

where, C_i and C_f are the initial and final concentration (mg/L) of metal ions in aqueous solution.

The amount of metal ions adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbent was determined using the equation :

$$Q = \frac{(C_i - C_f)V}{M} \quad (15)$$

where Q is the amount of selected metallic species adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbent (mg/g), C_i and C_e are the initial and equilibrium concentrations respectively (mg/L), M is the mass of adsorbent (g), and V is the volume of solution (L). The percent removal of metal ions was then calculated. All the kinetic parameters were carefully monitored and in each set of experiment only one parameter was varied keeping the others constant. All these experiments were conducted in triplicates so as to ascertain their reproducibility and cancel out human or instrumental errors.

In order to know the effect of presence of other heavy metals (Pb^{II} and Cd^{II}) in the solution on chromium removal efficiency of nanoparticles, similar experiments were carried out at optimum conditions using various concentrations of these metals in the solution. The original tannery effluent was collected from a tanning industry in Kanpur. It was first acid digested using standard method⁴⁹ and then treated with synthesized nanoparticles under the already optimized conditions for removal of chromium.

Conclusions

In this work magnetite nanoparticles were synthesized by using facile and hassle-free co-precipitation method and were used to remove hexavalent chromium from synthetic and real industrial wastewaters. These nanoparticles were analyzed and the average particle size was deter-

mined as 15.38 nm from XRD analysis, whereas, SEM micrographs showed agglomeration of these nanoparticles upon adsorption of chromium. Also, FT-IR analysis suggested slight shifts of bending and stretching vibrations of O-H and N-H groups upon adsorption of chromium. Batch adsorption studies suggested that pH of 2.0 and a temperature of 30 °C was optimum to achieved highest chromium removal. Moreover, these nanoparticles exhibited quite good degree of reusability (up to 5 cycles) for Cr^{VI} adsorption. At nanoparticle dosage of 4 g/L and an initial chromium concentration of 50 mg/L, the equilibrium time was 4 h with while for an initial concentration of 100 mg/L it was 6 h. The adsorption process followed pseudo-second order kinetic model and the calculated Q_e value (12.5 mg/g) was similar to observed Q_e value (12.0538 mg/g). Also, there was no sign of intra-particle diffusion in these nanoparticles. The process of Cr^{VI} sorption on iron oxide nanoparticles followed Langmuir isotherm because of successful fitting ($R^2 > 0.99$ and R.M.S. error < 0.027) and the maximum Cr^{VI} adsorptive capacity was found out as 16.3934 mg/g for 50 mg/L initial Cr^{VI} concentration. Thermodynamic analysis revealed that the adsorption process was spontaneous and endothermic, while randomness increased at the solid-liquid interface during Cr^{VI} adsorption. Batch adsorption study with these nanoparticles showed 72.45% Cr^{VI} removal from tannery effluent, revealing their capabilities to be used in for actual industrial wastewater remediation purposes. Agglomeration of nanoparticles had reduced actual available surface area. An attempt can be made to enhance adsorption capacity by modifying these nanoparticles with suitable ions or support materials that prevents agglomeration.

References

1. M. Moncur, J. Jambor, C. Ptacek and D. Blowes, *Appl. Geochem.*, 2009, **24**, 2362.
2. Y.-X. Liu, D.-X. Yuan, J.-M. Yan, Q.-L. Li and T. Ouyang, *J. Hazard. mater.*, 2011, **186**, 473.
3. S. Vasudevan, J. Lakshmi and R. Vanathi, *Clean-Soil, Air, Water*, 2010, **38**, 9.
4. V. Sundar, J. R. Rao and C. Muralidharan, *Journal of Cleaner*

- Production*, 2002, **10**, 69.
5. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), National primary drinking water regulations; final rule, *Fed. Regist.*, 1991, **56**, 3536.
 6. K. Brindha and L. Elango, *Water Resources Management*, 2012, **26**, 1747.
 7. S. Avudainayagam, M. Megharaj, G. Owens, R. S. Kookana, D. Chittleborough and R. Naidu, *Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 2003, **178**, 53.
 8. D. Beyersmann and A. Hartwig, *Archives of Toxicology*, 2008, **82**, 493.
 9. S. R. Shelnutz, P. Goad and D. V. Belsito, *CRC Critical Reviews in Toxicology*, 2007, **37**, 375.
 10. A. Dayan and A. Paine, *Human & Experimental Toxicology*, 2001, **20**, 439.
 11. A. Kabata-Pendias and A. B. Mukherjee, "Trace Elements from Soil to Human", 2007, Springer.
 12. A. Pechova and L. Pavlata, *Veterinarni Medicina-praha*, 2007, **52**, 1.
 13. M. Owlad, M. K. Aroua, W. A. W. Daud and S. Baroutian, *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution*, 2009, **200**, 59.
 14. Y. Nakano, K. Takeshita and T. Tsutsumi, *Water Research*, 2001, **35**, 496.
 15. D. D. Das, R. Mahapatra, J. Pradhan, S. N. Das and R. S. Thakur, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 2000, **232**, 235.
 16. S. J. Allen, Q. Gan, R. Matthews and P. A. Johnson, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 2005, **286**, 101.
 17. A. Hashem, R. Akasha, A. Ghith and D. Hussein, *Energy Edu. Sci. Technol.*, 2007, **19**, 69.
 18. A. Mittal, L. Krishnan and V. Gupta, *Sep. Purif. Technol.*, 2005, **43**, 125.
 19. K. Ravikumar, B. Deebika and K. Balu, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2005, **122**, 75.
 20. S. Gullapalli and M. S. Wong, *Chemical Engineering Progress*, 2011, **107**, 28.
 21. A. Figuerola, R. Di Corato, L. Manna and T. Pellegrino, *Pharmacol. Res.*, 2010, **62**, 126.
 22. X. Batlle and A. Labarta, *Journal of Physics D : Applied Physics*, 2002, **35**, R15.
 23. S. Laurent, D. Forge, M. Port, A. Roch, C. Robic, E. L. Vander and R. N. Muller, *Chem. Rev.*, 2008, **108**, 2064.
 24. R. M. Cornell and U. Schwertmann, "The iron oxides : Structure, properties, reactions, occurrences and uses", 2nd ed., Wiley-VCH, Weinheim 2003.
 25. G. Salazar Alvarez, "Synthesis, characterisation and applications of iron oxide nanoparticles", KTH, 2004.
 26. N. Devaraj, B. Ong and M. Matsumoto, *Synthesis and Reactivity in Inorganic, Metal-Organic and Nano-Metal Chemistry*, 2008, **38**, 204.
 27. L.-Y. Zhang, X.-J. Zhu, H.-W. Sun, G.-R. Chi, J.-X. Xu and Y.-I. Sun, *Current Applied Physics*, 2010, **10**, 828.
 28. K. A. Sidhaarth, J. Jeyanthi and N. Suryanarayana, *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 2012, **70**, 169.
 29. R. M. Cornell and U. Schwertmann, "The iron oxides : Structure, properties, reaction, occurrence and uses", VCH, Germany and USA, 1996.
 30. G. P. Gallios and M. Vaclavikova, *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 2008, **6**, 235.
 31. D. Mohan and C. U. Pittman (Jr.), *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2006, **137**, 762.
 32. S. R. Chowdhury and E. K. Yanful, *Journal of Environmental Management*, 2010, **91**, 2238.
 33. N. Shao-feng, L. Yong, X. Xin-hua and L. Zhang-hua, *Journal of Zhejiang University SCIENCE B*, 2005, **6**, 1022.
 34. C. Dhiwar, A. Tiwari and A. Bajpai, *Research on Chemical Intermediates*, 2012, **2**, 1.
 35. S. Lagergren, *Kungliga Svenska Vetenskapsakademiens Handlingar*, 1898, **24**, 1.
 36. Y.-S. Ho and G. McKay, *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 1998, **70**, 115.
 37. R. Subha and C. Namasivayam, *J. Environ. Eng. Manage.*, 2008 **18**, 275.
 38. W. Weber and J. Morris, *J. Sanit. Eng. Div. Am. Soc. Civ. Eng.*, 1963, **89**, 31.
 39. X. Xin, Q. Wei, J. Yang, L. Yan, R. Feng, G. Chen, B. Du and H. Li, *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 2012, **184**, 132.
 40. X. Lv, J. Xu, G. Jiang, J. Tang and X. Xu, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 2012, **369**, 460.
 41. V. Vadivelan and K. V. Kumar, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 2005, **286**, 90.
 42. I. Langmuir, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, **40**, 1361.
 43. H. Freundlich, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1906, **57**, 292.
 44. M. Temkin and V. Pyzhev, *Acta Physiochim. URSS*, 1940, **12**, 217.
 45. S. Basha, Z. Murthy and B. Jha, *Chemical. Engineering Journal*, 2008, **137**, 480.
 46. S. Shahmohammadi-Kalalagh, H. Babazadeh, A. Nazemi and M. Manshouri, *Casp. J. Env. Sci.*, 2011, **9**, 243.
 47. S.-Y. Zhao, D. K. Lee and Y. S. Kang, *Molecular Crystals and Liquid Crystals*, 2003, **407**, 429.
 48. C. Kril and R. Birringer, *Philosophical Magazine (A)*, 1998, **77**, 621.
 49. T. Martin, J. Creed and C. Brockhoff, EPA method 200.2 sample preparation procedure for spectrochemical determination of total recoverable elements, US Environmental Protection Agency, Cincinnati, 1994.

